

81° (Found: C, 78.30; H, 10.86. $C_{29}H_{48}O_8$ requires: C, 78.32; H, 10.87%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 745 (CH_3COO), 1 720 ($C=O$), 1 240 and 1 220 cm^{-1} ($C-O$); δ 2.02 (s, $C5-\alpha-O-COCH_3$), 1.2 ($ClO-CH_3$), 0.73 ($C13CH_3$), 0.93 and 0.83 (other CH_3).

Under similar reaction conditions, 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one semicarbazone (2; 2.0 g, m.p. 152°) furnished 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one (5; 0.75 g, 37.5%) on elution with petroleum ether-ether (30:1) which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 128° (lit.⁸ 129°). Further elution with petroleum ether-ether (28:1) yielded 3 β -chloro-7 α -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (8; 0.65 g, 32.5%), which failed to crystallise (Found: C, 72.68; H, 9.87. $C_{29}H_{47}ClO_8$ requires: C, 72.69; H, 9.88%); give positive Beilstein test; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 740 (CH_3COO), 1 715 ($C=O$), 1 235, 1 210 cm^{-1} ($C-O$) and 710 cm^{-1} ($C-Cl$); δ 5.35 (br s, C7- β H), 4.23 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 16 Hz, C3- α H), 2.00 (s, C7- $\alpha-O-COCH_3$), 1.18 ($ClO-CH_3$), 0.70 ($C13-CH_3$), 0.90 and 0.79 (other CH_3).

3 β -Acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one semicarbazone (3; m.p. 222°) under identical procedure conditions gave an oily residue which was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with light petroleum ether-ether (15:1) gave 3 β -hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (6; 0.65 g, 32.5%) which was crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 143° (lit.⁹ 142–43°). Further elution with petroleum ether-ether (10:1) furnished 3 β -hydroxy-7 α -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (9; 0.70 g, 40%), which was recrystallised from acetone 125° (Found: C, 75.58; H, 10.49. $C_{29}H_{48}O_4$ requires: C, 75.60; H, 10.50%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 450 (OH), 1 740 (CH_3COO), 1 720 ($C=O$), 1 230 and 1 215 cm^{-1} ($C-O$); δ 5.24 (br s C7- β H), 4.46 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3- α H), 2.5 (s, C3- β OH) 2.2 (s, C7- $\alpha-O-COCH_3$), 1.6 ($ClO-CH_3$), 0.75 ($C13-CH_3$), 0.92 and 0.80 (other CH_3). This on treatment with Ac_2O/Py gave the diacetate (10) as an oil (lit.¹⁰ oil).

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. S. A. A. Zaidi, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, for facilities and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

- SHAFIULLAH and H. ALI, *Syntheses*, 1979, 124.
- SHAFIULLAH and R. K. PATHAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 292.
- S. HUSAIN, V. AGARWAL and K. C. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, 27, 852.
- SHAFIULLAH, S. HUSAIN and D. M. BASHA, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1983, 114, 121.
- J. P. ANTHONY and J. WARKENTIN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, 57, 2681.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Wiley, New York, 1958, p. 189.
- C. W. SHOPPER, D. N. JONES, J. R. LEWIS and G. H. R. SUMMERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2876.
- A. WINDAUS and O. DALMER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1919, 52, 162.
- A. WINDAUS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3752.
- SHAFIULLAH, H. ALI and SHAMSUZZAMAN, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1981, 107, 97.

Studies in Spiro-heterocycles. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activities of some New Spiro(indolin-3,5'-pyrazolin)-1'-phenyl-2-ones and Spiro(indolin-3,5'-isoxazolin)-2-ones.

M. D. ANKHIWALA

Department of Chemistry, R. R. Mehta College of Science
Palanpur-385 002

Manuscript received 28 April 1989, revised 6 September 1989
accepted 4 January 1990

VARIOUS indole derivatives show varied biological activities¹. If the indole ring is joined to other heterocyclic systems through a spiro-carbon atom the resulting compounds show an increased spectrum of biological activities. Spiro-indoline-pyrazolines² and spiro-indoline-isoxazoline³ possess a wide range of biological activities.

Keeping the above observations in view, various spiro-pyrazolines and spiro-isoxazolines have been synthesised and screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities. 2-Hydroxyacetophenone derivatives (2) were prepared by the literature method⁴. Reaction of indolin-2,3-dione(isatin) (1) with 2-hydroxyacetophenone derivatives (2) in presence of diethylamine or piperidine base gave 3-hydroxy-3-phenacylindolin-2-ones (3)⁵. Dehydration of 3 by dilute hydrochloric acid or by hydrochloric acid in the presence of acetic acid gave 3-phenacylidene indoline-2-ones (4)⁵. Cyclocondensation of α,β -unsaturated ketone (4) with phenylhydrazine in equimolar amount in the presence of ethanol gave spiro-(indolin-3,5'-pyrazolin)-1'-phenyl-2-ones (5)⁶. Further, cyclocondensation of 4 with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in equimolar amount in the presence of ethanolic alkali gave spiro-(indolin-3,5'-isoxazolin)-2-ones (6)⁵ (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds have been supported by elemental, IR and pmr spectral analysis.

In compounds 5, IR bands have been observed in the regions 3 400–3 300 (OH), 3 100–2 800 (CH_2 , arom. and aliph.), 1 725–1 700 ($C=O$), 1 650–1 600 ($C=N$) and 1 240–1 220 cm^{-1} ($C-N$). In pmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of 5a, signals have been observed at δ 2.4 (s, CH_3) and 7.3–6.9 (m, ArH). In compounds 6, IR bands have been observed in the regions 1 730–1 700 ($C=O$) and 1 660–1 600 cm^{-1} ($C=N$). In pmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of 6a, signal have been observed at δ 2.6 (s, CH_3) and 7.5–6.8 (m, ArH).

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of spiro-pyrazolines and spiro-isoxazolines were carried out using cup-plate⁶ method at a concentration of 50 $\mu g ml^{-1}$ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasane serratia* and fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

Most of the compounds showed activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi (7–21 mm, zone of inhibition). Most of the compounds were found to be active against gram-(+) bacteria and

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5 AND 6*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula*
5a	H	OC ₂ H ₅	H	75	250	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃
5b	H	OC ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	83	280	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃
5c	H	OC ₂ H ₅	Br	82	235	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ BrN ₃ O ₃
5d	Br	OC ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	87	245	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ BrN ₃ O ₃
5e	H	OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	H	72	190	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₃
5f	H	OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	NO ₂	82	215	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₃
5g	H	OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	Br	86	242	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ BrN ₃ O ₃
5h	Br	OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	NO ₂	80	260	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ BrN ₃ O ₃
6a	H	OC ₂ H ₅	H	65	185	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄
6b	H	OC ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	71	162	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄
6c	H	OC ₂ H ₅	Br	69	171	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O ₄
6d	Br	OC ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	76	210	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₄
6e	H	OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	H	60	196	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄
6f	H	OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	NO ₂	66	225	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄
6g	H	OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	Br	64	160	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ BrN ₂ O ₄
6h	Br	OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	NO ₂	75	190	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ BrN ₂ O ₄

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Scheme 1

fungi (7–21 mm). Only few compounds like 5d, 5h, 6d and 6h were active against gram-(–) bacteria (10–16 mm). The results of antimicrobial activities of spiro-pyrazolines and spiro-isoxazolines (alongwith zone of inhibition in mm) are as follows: spiro-pyrazoline 5a (7–16), 5b (8–14), 5c (10–21),

5d (10–20), 5e (8–15), 5f (7–14), 5g (9–21) and 5h (8–18); spiro-isoxazoline 6a (8–16), 6b (8–15), 6c (11–19), 6d (10–18), 6e (7–16), 6f (7–15), 6g (10–21) and 6h (9–20). The increase in activity of the compounds may be attributed to the presence of bromine atom in the nucleus.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a XL-100A, 100-1 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard.

3-Hydroxy-3-phenacylindolin-2-ones (3) and 3-phenacylidene indolin-2-ones (4): The compounds were synthesised by literature method⁵.

Spiro-(indolin-3,5'-pyrazolin)-1'-phenyl-2-ones (5a–h): A mixture of 4 (0.01 mol) and phenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h using piperidine as a catalyst. After concentration and cooling, the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Spiro-(indolin-3,5'-isoxazolin)-2-ones (6a–h): A mixture of 4 (0.02 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.02 mol), potassium hydroxide (2 g), ethanol (100 ml) and water (2 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. After concentration and cooling, the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to the authorities of R. R. Mehta College of Science, Palanpur, for facilities.

References

1. Z. W. PAPANASTASION and J. L. NEWMAYER, US. Pat. 3 674 809/1972 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, 77, 126425); J. F. POLLETO, G. R. ALLEN, R. LITTELL and M. J. WELLS, US Pat. 3 801 594/1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 81, 3769); M. TAKAYAMA, M. NAKAO, M. KIMURA, S. INABA and H. YAMAMATO, US Pat. 424 954/1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 81, 77803).
2. H. G. LINDWALL and J. S. MCLENNAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4739; Z. H. KHALIL, *Z. Naturforsch.*, *Teil B*, 1978, 33, 105.
3. G. KOBAYASHI and Y. MATSUDA, Jap. Pat. 7 040 894/1970 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, 75, 20368); K. KIKUGAWA and M. ICHINO, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1973, 21, 1151.
4. R. ROBINSON and R. C. SHAH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1491, J. F. EIJKAMAN, F. BERGEMA and I. T. HEWARD, *Chem. Zentrablatt*, 1905, 1, 815
5. B. E. BAYOUMY, S. E. BAHAIFF and A. E. A. RAHMAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 520.
6. F. KAVANAGH, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic, New York, 1963, p. 126.

Scheme 1

Reactions of 2-(Fluoroaryl)-1H-indole-3-carboxaldehydes with Barbituric and Thiobarbituric Acids

KRISHNA C. JOSHI*, VIJAI N. PATHAK

and

RAGINI GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan,
Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 5 September 1988, revised 28 December 1989,
accepted 1 January 1990

HCNO and CO can be explained in terms of simple ring fissions⁵.

Fig. 1

PYRIMIDINETRIONES and pyrimidinediones display numerous biological activities¹. 5-Fluorouracil and other pyrimidines are reported to be potent anticancer agents². 5-Allyl-2,4,6-trioxo-5-hexahydropyrimidine- β -sulphooxypropanesulphonic acid displays pronounced antiinflammatory and analgesic activities accompanied by immunosuppressive effect observed in vitro³. 1-(Alkylideneamino)uracils are reported to be useful against weeds in cultivated plants⁴.

As part of our programme for developing new bioactive heterocycles, a number of 5-(2-fluoroaryl-1H-indol-3-ylmethylene)-2,4,6(1H,3H,5H)-pyrimidinetriones/dihydro-5-(2-aryl-1H-indol-3-ylmethylene)-2-thioxo-4,6(1H,5H)-pyrimidinediones (3) were synthesised through condensation of appropriate 2-(fluoroaryl)-1H-indole-3-carboxaldehyde (2) with barbituric/thiobarbituric acid in absolute ethanol. Formylation of appropriate 2-fluoroarylindole (1) with DMF-POCl₃ gave the desired 2-(fluoroaryl)-1H-indole-3-carboxaldehyde (2) (Scheme 1). In the mass spectrum, fragmentation of M⁺ peak of 3a at m/z 349 occurs via two characteristic pathways (a) and (b) (Fig. 1). Simultaneous loss of 2HNCO moieties from the molecular ion is characteristic of barbiturates (pathway-a). In pathway-b loss of

Herbicidal activity : Compounds 3d-f, 3h and 3i were evaluated for their herbicidal activity under submerged and up-land conditions during October-November. Effect of compounds on grass (*Panicum crusgalli*) and annual broad leaved weeds was tested in pre- as well as post-emergence stages under submerged condition at a dosage of 1 and 10 kg/ha. In the up-land condition crops tested were Japanese radish, sugar beet, soyabean germ and the weeds tested were *Polygonum blumei*, *Digitaria adscendens* and *Panicum crusgalli* at a dosage of 10 kg/ha in pre-emergence stage. All the compounds were found to be inactive.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr and ¹⁹F nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer using TMS as internal standard at 89.9 MHz and C₆F₆ as external standard at 84.25 MHz respectively, and mass spectra on Kratos 30 and 50 spectrometers. Elemental analyses were performed by Coleman 29 C, H and N analyser. All the compounds were homogeneous on tlc in various solvent systems.